

4Q36 (4QDeutⁱ) frag. 3 ii + PAM 43.667 frag. 72 (Deuteronomy 23:8–9)

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One should join the tiny unidentified fragment IAA Plate 93, frag. 67 (PAM 43.667 frag. 72; see DJD 33, plate VIII), with the letters תתע in line 1 and the top of a ל of a second line, to 4Q36 (4QDeutⁱ) frag. 3 ii in line 3 (published in DJD 14, p. 73; plate XIX). Textually, the tiny fragment continues with the text expected after לא; materially, the top edge of the fragment joins perfectly to the 4Q36 fragment. In addition, the joined fragments have the same stripes on the skin.

Gimp join of the two fragments: screenshot from sections of <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-360858> (blue) and of <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-502645> (red)

הַקִּלְלָה לְבִרְכָה כִּי [אֵהְבֶךָ יְהוָה אֱלֹהֶיךָ לֹא תִדְרֹשׁ שְׁלָמִים]	1
[וְטוֹבֵתֶם] כִּי [לְ] יָמֶיךָ לְעוֹלָם לֹא תִתְעַב אֲדָמִי כִּי אֶחֱיֶד הוּא]	2
לֹא תִתְעַב [בְּ] מִצְרַיִם כִּי גֵר הָיִיתָ בְּאֶרֶצוֹ בָּנִים אֲשֶׁר יוֹלְדוּ לָהֶם]	3
[דֹּרָשׁ] לְיִשְׁרָאֵל יָבוֹא לָהֶם בְּקֶהֱלָה יְהוָה]	4

References:

- DJD 14 Eugene Ulrich et al., *Qumran Cave 4, IX: Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Kings*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 14 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1995)
- DJD 33 Dana Pike and Andrew Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001)
- IAA Israel Antiquities Authority (used for reference to Plate numbers with scrolls fragments). Fragment numbers are those given by the IAA in The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, deadseascrolls.org.il
- PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum (used for references to PAM photographs).